

Symbolic threat from the West, belief in pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories, and attribution of blame for the war in Ukraine: A two-wave longitudinal study

Running head: Symbolic threat from West and conspiracy beliefs

Jakub Šrol¹ and Vladimíra Čavojová²

Centre of Social and Psychological Sciences, Slovak Academy of Sciences,

Dúbravská cesta 9, 841 04 Bratislava, Slovakia

¹ jakub.srol@savba.sk, ² vladimira.cavojova@savba.sk

This is author accepted version of manuscript:

Šrol, J., & Čavojová, V. (2025). Symbolic threat from the West, belief in pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories, and attribution of blame for the war in Ukraine: A two-wave longitudinal study. *Political Psychology*, 46(1), 85-103. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pops.12975>

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The study was supported by the Slovak Research and Development Agency as part of the research project APVV-20-0335: “*Reducing the spread of disinformation, pseudoscience, and bullshit*” and by the scientific grant agency of the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic as part of the project VEGA 2/0053/21: “*Examining unfounded beliefs about controversial social issues*”. Supplementary materials for this study are publicly available at: https://osf.io/amr7p/?view_only=1ddb7fd8ad134f1c874dde4728aec9d

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

JŠ: conception and design; data collection; data analysis and interpretation; manuscript drafting and revising; approval of final version of the submission

VČ: conception and design; data collection; data analysis and interpretation; manuscript drafting and revising; approval of final version of the submission

ABSTRACT

In this two-wave longitudinal study, we examined the sense of symbolic threat from the West and Russia as ideological roots of motivated belief in pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories and the attribution of blame to Russia, USA, and Ukraine for the war in Ukraine. Participants ($N = 690$) completed questionnaires on symbolic threat from the West and Russia, belief in pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories about the war in Ukraine as well as generic anti-West and anti-Russian conspiracy theories, and blame for the war in Ukraine. The sense of symbolic threat from the West and pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs predicted each other in time and were substantially associated with increased blaming of Ukraine and USA for the war in Ukraine. Conversely, symbolic threat from Russia along with the rejection of pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories predicted increased blaming of Russia over time. Motivated reasoning analyses suggested that the ideological link between the symbolic threat from the West and belief in anti-West conspiracy theories was stronger than the one between symbolic threat from Russia and belief in anti-Russian conspiracy theories. This suggests an existence of self-reinforcing relationship between the deep-rooted sense of symbolic threat and anti-West conspiracy theories which is exploited by various political actors.

Keywords: symbolic threat from the West; war in Ukraine; conspiracy beliefs; intergroup threat; motivated reasoning

Highlights

We examined symbolic threat as a predictor of belief in conspiracy theories

Symbolic threat from the West was associated with pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs

Both of these variables predicted increased blaming of USA and Ukraine for the war

Symbolic threat from Russia predicted decreased blaming of Russia for the war

Stronger ideological link existed for anti-West than anti-Russian conspiracy beliefs

INTRODUCTION

Immediately after the Russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022, few seemed to doubt who was the obvious villain (Putin) and who was the obvious victim (Ukraine) of this war. But soon thereafter, fierce pro-Kremlin propaganda coupled with a deep-rooted sense of symbolic threat from the West among segments of the population of many countries started to fuel narratives that blamed the USA and/or Ukraine itself for the conflict. The sense of symbolic threat from the West refers to the perception or feelings that one's identity, beliefs or values are being threatened by people, culture and policies of the Western world (Stephan et al., 2008; Stephan & Stephan, 2017) and is widespread in certain countries – either as a remnant of colonialism (especially in African and Asian countries) or the Cold War (in post-communist countries). Importantly, a symbolic threat from the West in post-communist countries of Eastern and Central Europe may be fueled by dissatisfaction with the political system and disappointment in democracy (Golias̄, 2021), and is hypothesized to be the driving force behind susceptibility to pro-Kremlin disinformation (Erlich & Garner, 2023; Mader et al., 2022). In some of these countries, such as Slovakia, the sense of symbolic threat from the West has been documented since the 19th century (Panczová, 2017) and later, it was reinforced by anti-West conspiracy theories that were a ubiquitous part of government propaganda during the communist regime (Kirziuk, 2021). And now, conspiracy theories associated with the symbolic threat from the West permeate the public discourse¹ and a March Globsec 2022 report showed that Slovakia had the highest percentage of people (42%) among the nine surveyed Central and Eastern European countries who viewed Western societies as a threat to their identity and values and approximately a quarter of the Slovak sample blamed the West for provoking the war in Ukraine. Surprisingly, despite their own history with Russian occupation, about a third of Slovaks still viewed Russia as a key strategic partner and believed that Russia was provoked into the war in Ukraine by the West (Globsec, 2022).

Although the sense of symbolic threat from the West and associated conspiracy theories are prevalent in new democracies of the former Soviet bloc (Globsec, 2022), their individual-level sources and socio-psychological consequences remain understudied. Therefore, in the present study, building on the assumption that conspiracy beliefs are rooted in social identity and threat-

¹ A recent example being when the former prime minister of Slovakia referred to the Slovak president, Zuzana Čaputová, as an “American agent”, who is following the orders given by the American embassy in Slovakia. Source: https://www.euractiv.com/section/politics/short_news/president-threatens-to-sue-critics-calling-her-an-american-agent/

related concerns (i.e. motivated), we aimed to examine the relationship between the sense of symbolic threat from the West and Russia, and the belief in pro-Kremlin conspiracy narratives that serve to justify Russia's role in the war in Ukraine. To this end, we explored the role of the symbolic threat from the West and Russia, as well as a range of demographic, cognitive, emotional, and political variables found in previous research to be correlated with conspiracy beliefs, in predicting pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs about the war at two time points shortly after the war in Ukraine began in March and May 2022. The two-wave data collection allowed us to explore potential changes in pro-Kremlin conspiracy theory endorsement and examine the longitudinal associations between the symbolic threat from the West and Russia, pro-Kremlin conspiracy theory beliefs, and attribution of blame to different actors (Russia, Ukraine, USA) for the war in Ukraine. Additionally, to examine the motivated nature of conspiracy beliefs, we tested whether the sense of symbolic threat from the West and Russia are differently associated with belief in anti-West and anti-Russian conspiracy theories, and whether analytical thinking moderates this relationship. This gave us a chance to examine both cognitive-motivational (motivated reasoning) and social identity-related factors (symbolic threat from the West and Russia) and their interaction in predicting conspiracy theory beliefs. Before outlining our research design, we summarize the theoretical and empirical findings on the role of intergroup threat and motivated reasoning in the adoption of conspiracy beliefs.

Conspiracy theories and intergroup threat

Conspiracy theory beliefs can be conceptualized as a form of collective motivated cognition (Krekó, 2015) and as such, they are intricately linked to the group's identity, stereotypes, motivations, beliefs and goals (Douglas et al., 2017, 2019; Hornsey et al., 2023). Conspiracy theories provide means to justify the group's prejudices and stereotypes, blame others for the problems of an in-group, as well as give people a meaningful explanation of their political and social reality. They portray a malevolent out-group that threatens the well-being of one's in-group (Mashuri et al., 2016) and thus serve to satisfy important social motives, namely to feel good about the groups one is a part of. This is because when people feel their group is marginalized or threatened, they tend to attribute perceived harm to conspiracy from other groups, rather than acknowledging internal issues (Douglas et al., 2019). Such perceived threat can be *realistic* (e.g. war or a pandemic) or *symbolic* – when people feel their goal or well-being is challenged or impeded by another group's actions, beliefs or characteristics as a way to compensate for their threatened needs (Douglas et al., 2019; Stephan & Stephan & 2017). Feelings of threat, realistic or symbolic, can then increase endorsement of conspiracy beliefs,

especially those portraying antagonistic groups responsible for the plight of the ingroup (van Prooijen, 2019).

In countries with historical suspicion against the West, the main villains in conspiracy theories may be figures or symbols of Western power. Individuals who feel powerless can be threatened by powerful others and are known to be more prone to conspiracy beliefs (Uscinski & Parent, 2014; Wood & Douglas, 2018). Even groups and nations may feel threatened by foreign powers, symbolized by their historical antagonists and conspiracy theories may serve as a means to regain the sense of power (Bruder et al., 2013; Nyhan & Reifler, 2010; Uscinski & Parent, 2014). For example, a study with Muslim participants (Nyhan & Zeitzoff, 2018) showed that belief in conspiracy theories was strongly associated with anti-West attitudes and feelings of lack of control. Similarly, in Muslim populations (Indonesia) belief in anti-Western conspiracy theories was higher when a threat to (Muslim) identity was made salient (Mashuri et al., 2016; Mashuri & Zaduqisti, 2015).

Although Muslim populations may experience symbolic threat due to their religion and historical grievances related to colonialism, these factors do not fully account for the significant sense of symbolic threat from the West in Eastern European countries. Even in the face of past Russian occupation, portions of their populations still perceive a greater threat from the West than the East. While historical and sociological reasons are often discussed (Kirziuk, 2021; Mesežnikov & Bartoš, 2021; Panczová, 2017), psychological research on the individual drivers of symbolic threat from the West remains limited. We need to better understand the processes that make people perceive threats from both West and Russia, leading to susceptibility to conspiracy theories. Psychological differences may arise in individuals perceiving a stronger symbolic threat from the West compared to those who sense higher symbolic threat from Russia. For example, while threat perception often aligns with conservative ideology, research reveals that conservatives and liberals differ in the types of threats they perceive (Clifton & Kerry, 2022; Kahn et al., 2022). While previously thought that symbolic threats have a greater impact on conservatives who see the world as a more dangerous place than liberals (e.g. Duckitt, 2001; White et al., 2019), recent research indicates that this link may be exaggerated (Clifton & Kerry, 2023). Although conservative people resist progressive societal changes, they may, at times, view the current status quo as threatening and engage in reactionary social change to promote greater social inequality (Becker, 2019; Clifton & Kerry, 2023). This perceived symbolic threat (either by the current establishment, if it is perceived as too progressive, or impeding social change) may cause conservatives to react in more authoritarian ways (Feldman

& Stenner, 1997). Conversely, liberals may feel more threatened by perceived threat to democracy by authoritarian regimes. Currently, Russia not only symbolizes such an authoritarian regime, but also poses military threat to neighboring countries (Lewis, 2020).

Motivated reasoning and the adoption of anti-West and anti-Russia conspiracy theories

Besides symbolic threats to one's identity, another important factor influencing the adoption of conspiracy beliefs is motivated reasoning, which involves interpreting information in a way that reinforces people's existing beliefs and attitudes (Miller et al., 2016). The motivated reasoning account clarifies why individuals with varying ideologies tend to embrace different conspiracy theories – usually those that discredit their political opponents (Miller et al., 2016; Van Bavel & Pereira, 2018). It also explains why political ideologies typically play a more significant role in predicting conspiracy beliefs compared to cognitive factors. People with higher analytic thinking or political knowledge may be better equipped to debunk improbable conspiracy theories when they oppose their worldviews, but they may not subject conspiracy theories that align with their beliefs to the same level of scrutiny. Several studies found evidence consistent with the motivated reasoning account, that higher cognitive dispositions may only make people more adept at interpreting information in line with their views (Drummond & Fischhoff, 2017; Miller et al., 2016). Based on this, we expected that those perceiving stronger symbolic threat from the West and weaker symbolic threat of Russia would endorse more anti-West and less anti-Russian conspiracy theories (and vice versa). We also aimed to explore whether analytic thinking ability would moderate this pattern.

Present study

To sum up, in the present study we examined both social identity-related and cognitive-motivational predictors of belief in pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories that serve to blame Ukraine and the West, and justify the role of Russia in the war in Ukraine. We included a range of demographic, cognitive, emotional and political predictors that were previously shown to be associated with beliefs in conspiracy theories to see if symbolic threat from the West and Russia would explain beliefs in pro-Kremlin conspiracy narratives about the war in Ukraine over and above these established predictors of conspiracy beliefs. However, for the sake of conciseness, we included the theoretical underpinnings and a summary of previous findings on demographic, emotional, cognitive, and political predictors of conspiracy beliefs in Section A of the Supplementary material. Our main goal was to examine whether social-identity related factors (symbolic threat from the West and Russia) predicted pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs at two

time points of data collection (March and May 2022). Importantly, the two-wave data collection allowed us to examine and predict potential changes in the symbolic threat from the West and Russia, belief in pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories, and changes in attribution of blame for the war in Ukraine to USA, Ukraine, and Russia. We hypothesized that the higher symbolic threat from the West and lower symbolic threat from Russia will be substantial predictors of pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs (over and above other more commonly examined predictors) and we assumed that all three of these factors will be related to lower attribution of blame to Russia for the war in Ukraine (in comparison with the blaming of Ukraine and USA). Although we did not have any strong assumptions about the psychological drivers of the sense of symbolic threat from the West and Russia, we planned to explore potential demographic, emotional, cognitive, and political predictors of these variables. Besides the role of social identity-related factors, we also drew from the motivated reasoning account (e.g. Miller et al., 2016) and examined cognitive-motivational underpinnings of belief in conspiracy theories about the West and Russia and their interaction with symbolic threat from the West and Russia. We expected that higher symbolic threat from the West would correlate with greater belief in conspiracy theories blaming the West or absolving Russia and that analytic thinking would moderate this politically motivated endorsement of conspiracy theories. Conversely, individuals with higher symbolic threat from Russia were expected to exhibit the opposite pattern of results that was hypothesized to likewise be moderated by analytic thinking ability.

METHODS

Participants and procedure

A participant recruitment agency distributed our online questionnaire created in Qualtrics to a quota sample of the adult Slovak population selected to be representative in terms of gender, age and region of residence. The first wave of online data collection took place between 22. – 24. 3. 2022, and the second one six weeks later (6.5 – 15.5. 2022)². In total, 900 people

² To provide context on prevailing mainstream and conspiracy narratives in Slovakia, we'll briefly outline key events between the two data collections. During the initial data collection period (March 22 – 24, 2022), occurring approximately a month after Vladimir Putin's launch of a 'special operation' for the demilitarization and denazification of Ukraine, public attention was primarily focused on the progress of the war. Notable events during this time included the occupation of the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant, which posed a nuclear disaster threat (Knowles et al., 2022), and the siege and bombing of Marioupol, including a hospital with a maternity ward. Images of a pregnant young influencer from the hospital were later exploited in disinformation campaigns (BBC, 2022). Media coverage was intense, with news from Ukraine dominating mainstream media in Slovakia. However, between the two data collection periods, it became increasingly evident that the war would not be

participated in the first wave of data collection, however, 210 (23.3%) did not respond to the invitation email to participate in the second wave. Thus, final sample consisted of 690 participants (363 women, 327 men) who provided complete data for both waves. Here, we report the results pertaining only to this sample with complete data. Participants were between 18 and 79 years old ($M = 45.8$, $SD = 13.15$). Concerning education, 24.3% of participants had elementary education or high school without a diploma, 39.3% had high school education with a diploma, and the rest (36.4%) attained some college or university education. Post hoc sensitivity analysis showed that the sample of 690 participants gave us sufficient statistical power ($\beta = .80$) to detect correlation coefficients of $r > .11$ with a 5% error probability. The survey also included some additional materials (on attitudes toward people from Ukraine and Russia and several personality measures) that were analyzed as part of another study and will not be discussed here.

Materials

Table 1 below presents the descriptive statistics and internal consistency estimates for the main variables and examines potential differences in symbolic threat from the West and Russia, endorsement of conspiracy beliefs, and the attribution of blame for the war in Ukraine in the two waves of data collection. Information about the materials used to measure the demographic, cognitive, emotional and political predictors and the descriptive statistics pertaining to those measures are included in Section B of the Supplementary material.

Symbolic threat from the West and Russia:

We asked participants to indicate on a 5-point scale (1 = *do not threaten my identity and values at all*, 5 = *threaten my identity and values very much*) how their identity and values feel threatened by Western countries and their way of life, the European Union, the USA, and the Russian Federation. The first three ratings were averaged to create a single variable reflecting the symbolic threat from the West. The single rating for the Russian Federation was used as a measure of the sense of symbolic threat posed by Russia.

short-lived. While some media commentators celebrated Ukraine's ability to defend against Russian forces and their retreat from the Kyiv region, others expressed concerns about the war's impact on the international economy, prices, and the strain of aiding Ukrainian refugees (Debiec, 2022). Slovak media extensively covered our prime minister's visit to Ukraine and pledged military support. Another significant media focus was on the atrocities committed against civilians as Ukrainian forces liberated occupied regions, such as the massacre of civilians and the discovery of mass graves in Buča (Browne et al., 2022). Even after news of the Buča massacres, opposition politicians remained resolute in their stance of refusing involvement in the conflict.

Belief in conspiracy theories:

Pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories. Participants indicated their agreement with seven conspiracy pro-Kremlin theories about the war in Ukraine on a 5-point scale (1= *totally disagree*, 5 = *totally agree*). The same statements were rated also during the second data collection.

Generic conspiracy theories. As an additional measure, participants were asked to indicate their agreement with seven generic conspiracy theories – e.g., related to the COVID-19 pandemic, chemtrails, and events of 9/11 on a 5-point scale (1= *totally disagree*, 5 = *totally agree*).

The full wordings of generic and pro-Kremlin conspiracy theory items along with their endorsement rates across the two waves of the data collection are provided in Section C of the Supplementary Material.

Anti-West and Anti-Russia conspiracy theories. In the second wave of the data collection, we added two anti-West conspiracy theories and two anti-Russia conspiracy theories (full wording of these items is given in Table 4 below). Although both scales included only two items, the two items of anti-West conspiracy theories ($r = .60$) and two items of anti-Russia conspiracy theories ($r = .43$) shared substantial mutual correlation suggesting considerable consistency of the answers.

Attribution of the blame for the war in Ukraine:

We asked participants to what degree they think Ukraine, Russia, and USA are responsible for the war in Ukraine. Participants gave their ratings on a ten-point scale (1= *not at all responsible*, 10 = *totally responsible*) separately for every actor.

RESULTS

Analyses were conducted in jamovi 2.3 software (The jamovi project, 2022) and using the *lavaan* package in R software (Rosseel, 2012). As a first step in our analyses, we examined the longitudinal relationships between the symbolic threat from the West and Russia and pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs about the war in Ukraine using a set of hierarchical linear regressions in which we accounted for the autoregressive effects and controlled for a range of potential demographic, emotional, cognitive and political predictors of those variables. In a similar vein, we looked at the longitudinal changes in the attribution of blame for the war in Ukraine and how these changes were associated with pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs and the

symbolic threat from the West and Russia. Finally, to explore whether people with a stronger symbolic threat of the West or Russia are more susceptible to believing conspiracy theories in general or rather whether they believe more only those conspiracy narratives that fit into their worldview, we tested several moderation models where the symbolic threat from the West and Russia were included as predictors of anti-West and anti-Russia conspiracy beliefs with analytic thinking as a moderator.

----- **INSERT TABLE 1 AROUND HERE** -----

Predicting belief in pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories about the war in Ukraine and the sense of symbolic threat from the West and Russia

To examine the longitudinal associations between our predictor variables (demographic, cognitive, emotional and political), the sense of symbolic threat from the West and Russia, and the belief in pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories, we conducted a series of hierarchical regression analyses (correlations between the main variables in the study are presented in Section D in the Supplementary material). These included three regressions where the symbolic threat from the West and Russia and belief in pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories at the second wave of the data collection were included as outcome variables while the same variables from the first wave were included (thus controlling for the autoregressive effects, i.e. the stability of the variables between the first and second wave of the data collection), along with demographic, cognitive, emotional and political variables, as predictors³. The results are summarized in Table 2.

First, both symbolic threat from the West (positively) and symbolic threat from Russia (negatively) significantly predicted the endorsement of pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories in the second wave. Higher age, lower education, preference for autocratic government and political cynicism were likewise significantly associated with the increased endorsement of pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs over time. When it comes to predicting the sense of symbolic threat from the West, the results of the regression were very similar to those mentioned above. Both symbolic threat from Russia (negatively) and pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs predicted increased sense of symbolic threat from the West. Thus, while we hypothesized that the symbolic threat would

³ We opted for this approach instead of the perhaps more standard cross-lagged panel model analysis as with our two waves of data collection, the cross-lagged panel models would always be just identified and therefore, would not give any information about the actual fit of the models. However, for an interested reader, we also supplement our analyses based on hierarchical linear regression in which we control for the autoregressive effects by reporting the results of the cross-lagged panel model analyses for our key hypotheses in Section F of the Supplementary materials. Please note that both of the analyses are consistent in that they give substantially the same key results.

longitudinally predict the endorsement of pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories rather than vice versa, this was not corroborated by the results, as both of the variables seemed to predict each other in time (this is likewise corroborated by a cross-lagged panel model analysis presented in Section F of the Supplementary material). Apart from this, higher age, political conservatism and political cynicism also predicted the increased symbolic threat from the West.

Interestingly, after accounting for the stability of the symbolic threat from Russia between the two study waves, we found the only significant predictor of this variable to be the lower symbolic threat of the West, although it could be mentioned that helplessness was both marginally significant predictor in the regression ($p = .063$) and was correlated with the symbolic threat from Russia in both waves of the study (see Table S4 in Section D of the Supplementary material).⁴

----- INSERT TABLE 2 AROUND HERE -----

Symbolic threat from the West and Russia, pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs, and the attribution of blame for the war in Ukraine

As the final step in our analyses, we examined how were the symbolic threat from the West and Russia, as well as pro-Kremlin conspiracy theory beliefs, longitudinally associated with the attribution of blame for the war in Ukraine to Russia, Ukraine, and USA. Therefore, we conducted three hierarchical linear regressions where we predicted blaming of different actors in the second wave by their blame ratings in the first wave of the study (to account for the stability of the blame ratings) and in the second step, we added symbolic threat variables and pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs as predictors.

As can be seen from Table 3, both symbolic threat from the West and pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs predicted increased blaming of USA and Ukraine and decreased blaming of Russia over time. Not surprisingly, symbolic threat from Russia was associated positively with the

⁴ We also performed regression analyses with the same variables as predictors of belief in generic conspiracy theories (not related to the war in Ukraine) in the two waves of data collection. The results (see Section E of the Supplementary material) show a similar pattern of results as those presented above, especially when it comes to the mutual longitudinal relationship between the symbolic threat from the West and belief in generic conspiracy theories. In the discussion, we offer two possible interpretations for the strong associations found between symbolic threat from the West and both pro-Kremlin and generic conspiracy theory beliefs.

attribution of blame to Russia, and negatively with blaming USA for the war in Ukraine, but it did not significantly predict the attribution of blame to Ukraine. As a supplementary analysis, we examined the longitudinal associations between blame ratings and other variables via cross-lagged panel models (see Section F of the Supplementary material). These analyses showed that there was no difference in cross-lagged paths between either of the symbolic threats or pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs and blaming of USA in the two waves of the study. However, the cross-lagged paths from the symbolic threat of the West and pro-Kremlin conspiracy theory beliefs predicting attribution of blame to Ukraine (positively) and Russia (negatively) were all significantly stronger than the paths in the opposite direction. This provides evidence that people with a stronger sense of symbolic threat from the West and higher endorsement of pro-Kremlin conspiracy theory beliefs blamed Ukraine increasingly more and, at the same time, absolved Russia from its responsibility for the war in Ukraine in the first months of the war.

----- INSERT TABLE 3 AROUND HERE -----

A motivated reasoning analysis of the link between the symbolic threat from the West and Russia and belief in anti-West and anti-Russia conspiracy theories

To investigate whether individuals with a stronger symbolic threat from the West or Russia are more prone to believing conspiracy theories in general or whether they only believe more those conspiracy theories that align with their worldview, we conducted multiple analyses with our anti-West and anti-Russia conspiracy theory items. Table 4 shows that the symbolic threat from the West was strongly positively correlated with the belief in anti-West conspiracy theories but was only very weakly negatively associated with the belief in anti-Russian conspiracy theories. Conversely, the correlations with the symbolic threat from Russia were all in the moderate range and were positive in the case of Anti-Russian and negative in the case of Anti-West conspiracy theory beliefs. This supports the motivated reasoning account – those perceiving symbolic threats from the West tend to endorse conspiracy theories blaming the West, while those sensing threats from Russia tend to believe in conspiracy theories portraying Russia negatively. However, it is obvious that the correlation between the symbolic threat from the West and belief in anti-West conspiracy theories was much stronger than the one between the symbolic threat from Russia and anti-Russian conspiracy theory beliefs, as proved by the difference between the values after Fisher's r-to-Z Transformation ($z = 11.68, p < .001$).

To examine whether this politically motivated endorsement of conspiracy theories gets more or rather less pronounced among people with higher levels of dispositions that might make them more capable of interpreting evidence in their own favor, we ran moderation analyses where we used the symbolic threat from the West and Russia as predictors of belief in anti-West or anti-Russia conspiracy theories (we used average ratings of both items for this analysis) with analytic thinking as a moderator (Table 5).

----- **INSERT TABLE 4 AROUND HERE** -----

Both the symbolic threat from the West and Russia were significant predictors of anti-West conspiracy theories but in both models, there was also a significant moderation effect (the interaction was only marginally significant in the case of symbolic threat from Russia). Simple slope analyses show that although symbolic threat from the West positively and symbolic threat from Russia negatively predicted belief in anti-West conspiracy theories at all levels of analytic thinking, the relationships were stronger among those with higher analytic thinking. The same was not true for anti-Russian conspiracy theory beliefs. While both symbolic threats from the West and Russia, as well as analytic thinking predicted those beliefs, there was no significant interaction present in either one of the models. Both the correlation and moderation analyses provide more robust evidence for motivated reasoning in the context of a stronger ideological link between symbolic threat from the West and anti-West conspiracy beliefs, compared to symbolic threat from Russia and anti-Russian conspiracy beliefs.

----- **INSERT TABLE 5 AROUND HERE** -----

DISCUSSION

The main aim of this paper was to examine how social identity-related factors and motivated cognition contribute to people's susceptibility to conspiracy theories used for propagandistic purposes in assigning blame for the war in Ukraine. The use of data from Slovakia provides a unique setting, given Slovakia's proximity to the war in Ukraine and the fact that Slovakia is a known long-term subject to Russian disinformation campaigns (Ružičková, 2023; Smoleňová, 2015). Our data clearly shows that spreading conspiracy theories about the war in Ukraine is "effective": there is a substantial link between the symbolic threat from the West and the

endorsement of pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories. Crucially, people who endorse pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories and perceive stronger symbolic threat from the West blamed Ukraine and the USA increasingly more for the war in Ukraine over time. While the symbolic threat from Russia did not appear to contribute much to these blame ratings, it predicted, along with the rejection of pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories, increased blaming of Russia over time.

We also attempted to disentangle the relationships between the endorsement of pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories and the symbolic threat from the West and Russia by examining their longitudinal associations. While we expected that the symbolic threat variables would predict the increased endorsement of pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories over time, the results were much less clear-cut. Rather, we found that the symbolic threat (especially from the West) and pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories predict each other in time, suggesting that the disseminators of pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories can rely on deep-rooted suspicions of a substantial proportion of the Slovak population against the USA specifically and West in general. In turn, conspiracy theories aimed against the USA and the West enhance the feelings of symbolic threat from the West, creating the vicious circle of purported enemies, feelings of threat and subsequent acceptance of conspiracy explanations alleging the role of Western powers conspiring against Slovaks, who must turn to Russia as their stronger Slavic “brother” for support and protection. This aligns with van Prooijen's threat model (2019), which posits that when individuals perceive existential threats, especially in the presence of an antagonistic group (in this case USA) that they can blame as the initial cause of the threat, they tend to turn to conspiracy theories as a convenient means of escaping an anxious state. This self-reinforcing relationship between threat and conspiracy theories was extensively exploited by some Slovak politicians who actively pursued conspiracy explanations since the beginning of the Russian invasion to undermine the government's decision to send military help to Ukraine⁵. For example, former PM Robert Fico challenged the gifting of S-300 defense system to Ukraine and claimed that Slovakia “is dragged” to the war and it should instead maintain peace, he alleged that Slovakia lost its defense by gifting the S-300 system (Hudec, 2022) and likened NATO soldiers to Nazi troops⁶.

⁵ PM Eduard Heger's government strongly supported the West and Ukraine. They swiftly responded to Ukrainian refugees and aided Ukraine's defense (Ogrodnik, 2022). In collaboration with the EU, Slovakia provided older Russian military equipment, including tanks and S-300 anti-aircraft defense systems, in exchange for newer systems promised by the EU. In April 2021 Slovak PM visited Ukraine and met with Volodymyr Zelensky.

⁶ <https://www.euractiv.com/section/politics/news/eu-socialists-quiet-as-slovak-member-spreads-kremlin-propaganda/>

Besides the higher symbolic threat from the West and the lower symbolic threat from Russia, increased belief in pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories was predicted by higher age, lower education, slightly higher preference for authoritarian government and political cynicism. Interestingly, increased symbolic threat from the West was predicted by similar variables, but none of the demographic and psychological factors predicted symbolic threat of Russia. This suggests a substantial overlap between the potential psychological sources of the sense of symbolic threat from the West and belief in pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories. Moreover, these variables shared unusually high correlations among each other, as well as with our additional measure of generic conspiracy beliefs (r 's between .68 – .97; see Section D and E in the Supplementary material). Although our data do not allow for definitive interpretation of these robust correlations between generic and pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs and symbolic threat from West, two possible explanations can be considered. First, even though the generic conspiracy theories (such as those related to COVID-19) included in our study were not explicitly anti-West, participants with higher symbolic threat from the West might be more inclined to believe them because they were spread by the same sources on social media, where communities can serve as echo-chambers (Cinelli et al., 2022), and much COVID-19-related disinformation was spread by pro-Russian servers (Politico, 2022; Toepfl et al., 2022) with the aim to destabilize Western countries.

Second, generic and pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs and symbolic threat from West probably share common psychological correlates, such as lower cognitive reflection, political conservatism, preference for authoritarian leaders and political cynicism. Both conservatism and lower cognitive reflection have been previously shown to make people more vulnerable to adopting conspiracy theories (van der Linden et al., 2021; Nera et al., 2021; Romer & Jamieson, 2020; but see Enders et al., 2022). This vulnerability may be exploited by producers of disinformation aimed at more conservative viewers, and once people fall for a conspiracy theory that may seem plausible and consistent with their worldview, they become more vulnerable to new, even unrelated conspiracy theories (van Mulukom et al., 2022). As suggested by Becker (2019), if conservatives feel threatened by too progressive societal changes, they may resort to more authoritarian responses – and conspiracy theories heightening the symbolic threat from West may utilize these narratives, e.g. by claiming that West and liberals want to jeopardize the “traditional family”. Moreover, conservatives have been shown to display a higher preference for associating with others similar to oneself in political ideology (Boutyline & Willer, 2017) and being less affected by a heterogenous mix of stories

(“breaking from filter bubbles”; Rhodes, 2022) which may increase their vulnerability to disinformation coming from their “trusted sources” even more. Besides psychological **factors**, generic and pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs and symbolic threat from West shared also some of the demographic **correlates**, such as lower education and lower perceived socioeconomic status. This finding is in line with precarity hypothesis suggested by Adam-Troian et al. (2023) that the subjective experience of permanent insecurity stemming from objective material strain is connected with lower trust in authorities and higher belief in conspiracy theories. It may suggest that existential threat posed by the war in neighboring country following the pandemic years was especially hard for the people who found themselves in precarious conditions and made them an easier target for disinformators.

Lastly, our results showed evidence of motivated reasoning in that people tended to believe more those conspiracy theories that fit their worldview (Miller et al., 2016). However, this effect was not symmetrical for the belief in anti-West and anti-Russian conspiracy beliefs. Rather, the ideological link between the symbolic threat from the West and belief in anti-West conspiracy theories was much stronger than the one between the symbolic threat from Russia and belief in anti-Russian conspiracy theories. Likewise, this link was moderated by analytic thinking – suggesting that those who are more adept at interpreting evidence in their favor are actually more, not less susceptible to believing unfounded beliefs that fit their worldview (see Drummond & Fischhoff, 2017) – but only in the case of anti-West, not anti-Russian conspiracy theory beliefs. A similar asymmetry was found by Miller et al. (2016) in the case of the politically motivated endorsement of conspiracy theories among conservatives and liberals. They argued that for conservatives, embracing conspiracy theories may be a more effective means of reinforcing their worldviews than it is for liberals. While the symbolic threat from the West cannot be equated with political conservatism, both correlational and regression results in our study suggest that the symbolic threat from the West was much stronger among the more conservative participants. Moreover, narratives that build on the symbolic threat from the West have both a long history in some of the countries of the former Soviet Union, such as Slovakia (Kirziuk, 2021; Panczová, 2017), and are to this day used by politicians in Slovakia (Dubóczy & Škríbová, 2022). This could explain a stronger ideological link with the endorsement of conspiracy theories in the case of symbolic threat from the West in comparison with Russia.

Limitations

It should be noted that the present study had several limitations. First, due to budgetary constraints and a relatively large drop-out rate between the two waves of the present study, we

were unable to conduct the third wave of measurement. This was unfortunate as the three-wave study would have allowed us to conduct longitudinal mediations that could contribute to our better understanding of the relationship between the sense of symbolic threat of the West and Russia, pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs, and the attribution of blame for the war in Ukraine. Secondly, even though we theorized that the symbolic threat would drive the belief in pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories and that these variables would both drive the attribution of blame for the war in Ukraine in our study and we used a two-wave design to examine longitudinal associations between these variables, we cannot provide strong evidence to support the cause-effect relationships. While the narratives involving the symbolic threat from the West have a long history in Slovakia (Kirziuk, 2021; Panczová, 2017) and pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories about the war in Ukraine are relatively new, suggesting that they might be driven by the symbolic threat from the West rather than vice versa, our longitudinal analyses suggested that these variables predict each other in time (i.e. the longitudinal paths were not significantly stronger for the symbolic threat variables predicting pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs than vice versa). As shown in our study, these variables were related to such an extent, that it would likely be impossible to disentangle their predictive patterns in such a short time frame as employed in the present study. And while the longitudinal predictive patterns in the case of the attribution of blame for the war in Ukraine support the predictive role of the symbolic threat variables and pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs in time much more clearly (see Section f of the Supplementary material), even in this case it has to be noted that the regression-based analyses cannot provide clear evidence for any causal effects and thus any such interpretations need to be cautious in this regard.

Conclusion

Our results showed that the feeling that one's identity and values are threatened by Western countries and their way of life is substantially linked with the belief in pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories and attribution of blame to the USA and Ukraine, rather than Russia, for the war in Ukraine. While the main variables of interest to us changed relatively little overall in the six weeks between the two waves of the study, we still found that the longitudinal changes in the sense of symbolic threat and pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs were associated with quite substantial changes in the attribution of blame for the war in Ukraine. The sense of symbolic threat from the West may likely have been driven by narratives exploited by certain vocal Slovak politicians in the given period, who actively blamed the West and specifically the USA

for the continuation of the war in Ukraine (Dubóczy & Škríbová, 2022) and seemingly succeeded in making people more prone to believe also pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories.

In future research, we think it would be worthwhile to focus on the segment of the population that seems to be more prone to believing new conspiracy theories and examine the predictors of the changes in their beliefs at a within-subject level over longer periods of time. It would also be beneficial to replicate the present study in multiple countries with varying degrees of the symbolic threat from the West and Russia, such as Poland and the Baltic states (where there is a strong sense of symbolic threat from Russia) or Hungary, which may have similar levels of symbolic threat from the West as Slovakia, but also in countries and regions outside of Central and Eastern Europe. While support for Ukraine appears to be unshakable in many countries around the world at present, the spread of pro-Kremlin disinformation justifying Russia's role and blaming Ukraine or the West for the war has the potential to alter public perceptions in this regard over time. For these reasons, we believe that this study represents an important attempt to understand the psychological mechanisms that contribute to the spread of such disinformation and its potential consequences.

DATA ACCESSIBILITY STATEMENT

The conducted study and analysis plan presented in this manuscript were not preregistered. Data for this study are publicly available at: https://osf.io/amr7p/?view_only=c223ce1df05f455d8e0b2b15861d9422

REFERENCES

- Adam-Troian, J., Chayinska, M., Paladino, M. P., Uluğ, Ö. M., Vaes, J., & Wagner-Egger, P. (2023). Of precarity and conspiracy: Introducing a socio-functional model of conspiracy beliefs. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 62(S1), 136–159. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjso.12597>
- BBC News. (2022). *Ukraine war: Three dead as maternity hospital hit by Russian air strike*. BBC NEWS. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-60675599>
- Becker, J. C. (2020). Ideology and the promotion of social change. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences*, 34, 6-11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cobeha.2019.10.005>

- Boutyline, A., & Willer, R. (2017). The Social Structure of Political Echo Chambers: Variation in Ideological Homophily in Online Networks: Political Echo Chambers. *Political Psychology*, 38(3), 551–569. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pops.12337>
- Browne, M., Botti, D., & Willis, H. (2022). *Satellite images show bodies lay in Bucha for weeks, despite Russian claims.* The New York Times. <https://www.nytimes.com/2022/04/04/world/europe/bucha-ukraine-bodies.html>
- Bruder, M., Haffke, P., Neave, N., Nouripanah, N., & Imhoff, R. (2013). Measuring individual differences in generic beliefs in conspiracy theories across cultures: Conspiracy mentality questionnaire. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 4(April), 225. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00225>
- Cinelli, M., Etta, G., Avasse, M., Quattrocioni, A., Di Marco, N., Valensise, C., Galeazzi, A., & Quattrocioni, W. (2022). Conspiracy theories and social media platforms. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 47, 101407. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2022.101407>
- Clifton, J. D. W., & Kerry, N. (2022). Belief in a Dangerous World Does Not Explain Substantial Variance in Political Attitudes, But Other World Beliefs Do. *Social Psychological and Personality Science*, 194855062211193. <https://doi.org/10.1177/19485506221119324>
- Dębiec, K. (2022). *Slovakia: Strategic dilemmas after the Russian invasion of Ukraine.* OSW Centre for Eastern Studies. <https://www.osw.waw.pl/en/publikacje/osw-commentary/2022-05-10/slovakia-strategic-dilemmas-after-russian-invasion-ukraine>
- Douglas, K. M., Sutton, R. M., & Cichocka, A. (2017). The psychology of conspiracy theories. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 26(6), 538–542. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721417718261>
- Douglas, K. M., Uscinski, J. E., Sutton, R. M., Cichocka, A., Nefes, T., Ang, C. S., & Deravi, F. (2019). Understanding conspiracy theories. *Political Psychology*, 40(S1), 3–35. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pops.12568>
- Drummond, C., & Fischhoff, B. (2017). Individuals with greater science literacy and education have more polarized beliefs on controversial science topics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 114(36), 9587–9592.
- Dubóczy, P., & Škríbová, S. (2022). *Slovak far-right politicians are spreading false narratives about refugees, the West is being blamed for the ongoing energy crisis.* <https://www.freiheit.org/central-europe-and-baltic-states/slovak-far-right-politicians-are-spreading-false-narratives-about>

- Duckitt, J. (2001). A dual-process cognitive-motivational theory of ideology and prejudice. *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*, 33, 41–113. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601\(01\)80004-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601(01)80004-6)
- Enders, A., Farhart, C., Miller, J., Uscinski, J., Saunders, K., & Drochon, H. (2022). Are Republicans and Conservatives More Likely to Believe Conspiracy Theories? *Political Behavior*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11109-022-09812-3>
- Erlich, A., & Garner, C. (2023). Is pro-Kremlin Disinformation Effective? Evidence from Ukraine. *The International Journal of Press/Politics*, 28(1), 5–28. <https://doi.org/10.1177/19401612211045221>
- Feldman, S., & Stenner, K. (1997). Perceived Threat and Authoritarianism. *Political Psychology*, 18(4), 741–770. <https://doi.org/10.1111/0162-895X.00077>
- Globsec. (2022). *GLOBSEC Trends 2022*. GLOBSEC - A Global Think Tank: Ideas Shaping the World. <https://www.globsec.org/sites/default/files/2022-05/GLOBSEC-Trends-2022.pdf>
- Goliaš, P. (2021). *Takmer polovica občanov Slovenska nie je spokojná s kvalitou demokracie*. INEKO. <https://www.ineko.sk/clanky/publikacie>
- Hudec, M. (2022). *Ex-PM Fico says Slovakia should stop helping Ukraine*. EURACTIV. https://www.euractiv.com/section/politics/short_news/ex-pm-fico-says-slovakia-should-stop-helping-ukraine/
- Kahn, D. T., Björklund, F., & Hirschberger, G. (2022). The intent and extent of collective threats: A data-driven conceptualization of collective threats and their relation to political preferences. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 151(5), 1178–1198. <https://doi.org/10.1037/xge0000868>
- Kirziuk, A. (2021). “By the order of their foreign masters” Soviet dissidents, anti-Western conspiracy, and the deprivation of agency. In *Conspiracy Theories in Eastern Europe* (pp. 67–86). Routledge.
- Knowles, H., Kornfield, M., Mufson, S., & Suliman, A. (2022). Russian forces seize Ukrainian nuclear power plant after shelling sets it on fire. *The Washington Post*. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/world/2022/03/03/nuclear-power-plant-fire-ukraine-zaporizhzhia/>
- Krekó, P. (2015). Conspiracy theory as collective motivated cognition. In *The psychology of Conspiracy*. Routledge.
- Lewis, D. G. (2020). *Russia's New Authoritarianism: Putin and the Politics of Order*. Edinburgh University Press. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/10.3366/j.ctv10kmcxz>

- Mader, M., Marinov, N., & Schoen, H. (2022). Foreign Anti-Mainstream Propaganda and Democratic Publics. *Comparative Political Studies*, 55(10), 1732–1764. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00104140211060277>
- Mashuri, A., & Zaduqisti, E. (2015). The Effect of Intergroup Threat and Social Identity Salience on the Belief in Conspiracy Theories over Terrorism in Indonesia: Collective Angst as a Mediator. *International Journal of Psychological Research*, 8(1), 24–35.
- Mashuri, A., Zaduqisti, E., Sukmawati, F., Sakdiah, H., & Suharini, N. (2016). The Role of Identity Subversion in Structuring the Effects of Intergroup Threats and Negative Emotions on Belief in Anti-West Conspiracy Theories in Indonesia. *Psychology and Developing Societies*, 28(1), 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0971333615622893>
- Miller, J. M., Saunders, K. L., & Farhart, C. E. (2016). Conspiracy Endorsement as Motivated Reasoning: The Moderating Roles of Political Knowledge and Trust. *American Journal of Political Science*, 60(4), 824–844. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajps.12234>
- Nera, K., Wagner-Egger, P., Bertin, P., Douglas, K. M., & Klein, O. (2021). A power-challenging theory of society, or a conservative mindset? Upward and downward conspiracy theories as ideologically distinct beliefs. *European Journal of Social Psychology*, 51(4–5), 740–757. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejsp.2769>
- Nyhan, B., & Reifler, J. (2010). When Corrections Fail: The Persistence of Political Misperceptions. *Political Behavior*, 32(2), 303–330. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11109-010-9112-2>
- Nyhan, B., & Zeitzoff, T. (2018). Conspiracy and Misperception Belief in the Middle East and North Africa. *The Journal of Politics*, 80(4), 1400–1404. <https://doi.org/10.1086/698663>
- Ogrodnik, Ł. (2022). *Slovakia's Response to the Russian Invasion of Ukraine*. PISM. The Polish Institute of International Affairs. <https://pism.pl/publications/slovakias-response-to-the-russian-invasion-of-ukraine>
- Panczová, Z. (2017). The Image of the West in Conspiracy Theories in Slovakia and Its Historical Context. *Folklore: Electronic Journal of Folklore*, 69, 49–68. <https://doi.org/10.7592/FEJF2017.69.panczova>
- Politico. (2022, March 17). Anti-vax conspiracy groups lean into pro-Kremlin propaganda in Ukraine. <https://www.politico.eu/article/antivax-conspiracy-lean-pro-kremlin-propaganda-ukraine/>

- Rhodes, S. C. (2022). Filter Bubbles, Echo Chambers, and Fake News: How Social Media Conditions Individuals to Be Less Critical of Political Misinformation. *Political Communication*, 39(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10584609.2021.1910887>
- Romer, D., & Jamieson, K. H. (2020). Conspiracy theories as barriers to controlling the spread of COVID-19 in the U.S. *Social Science & Medicine*, 113356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2020.113356>
- Rosseel, Y. (2012). lavaan: An R package for structural equation modeling. *Journal of statistical software*, 48, 1-36.
- Ružičková, M. (2023). Russian Bear of Influence in Slovakia. *Warsaw Institute*. <https://warsawinstitute.org/russian-bear-of-influence-in-slovakia/>
- Smoleňová, I. (2015). *The pro-Russian disinformation campaign in the Czech republic and Slovakia*. Prague Security Studies Institute (PSSI).
- Stephan, W. G., Renfro, C. L., & Davis, M. D. (2008). The Role of Threat in Intergroup Relations. In U. Wagner, L. R. Tropp, G. Finchilescu, & C. Tredoux (Eds.), *Improving Intergroup Relations* (1st ed., pp. 55–72). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444303117.ch5>
- Stephan, W. & Stephan, C. (2017). Intergroup threat theory. *The international encyclopedia of cultural communication*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc. pp.1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118783665.ieicc0162>
- The jamovi project (2022). jamovi (Version 2.3) [Computer Software]. Retrieved from <https://www.jamovi.org>
- Toepfl, F., Kravets, D., Ryzhova, A., & Beseler, A. (2022). Who are the plotters behind the pandemic? Comparing Covid-19 conspiracy theories in Google search results across five key target countries of Russia's foreign communication. *Information, Communication & Society*, 0(0), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2022.2065213>
- Uscinski, J., & Parent, J. M. (2014). *American conspiracy theories*. Oxford University Press.
- van Mulukom, V., Pummerer, L. J., Alper, S., Bai, H., Čavojová, V., Farias, J., Kay, C. S., Lazarevic, L. B., Lobato, E. J. C., Marinthe, G., Banai, I. P., Šrol, J., & Žeželj, I. (2022). Antecedents and consequences of COVID-19 conspiracy beliefs: A systematic review. *Social Science & Medicine*, 301, 114912. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SOCSCIMED.2022.114912>

- van der Linden, S., Panagopoulos, C., Azevedo, F., & Jost, J. T. (2021). The Paranoid Style in American Politics Revisited: An Ideological Asymmetry in Conspiratorial Thinking. *Political Psychology, 42*(1), 23–51. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pops.12681>
- van Prooijen, J. W. (2019). An existential threat model of conspiracy theories. *European Psychologist, 25*(1), 16–25.
- White, K. R., Kinney, D., Danek, R. H., Smith, B., & Harben, C. (2020). The Resistance to Change-Beliefs Scale: Validation of a new measure of conservative ideology. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin, 46*(1), 20-35.
- Wood, M. J., & Douglas, K. M. (2019). Conspiracy theory psychology: Individual differences, worldviews, and states of mind. In J. E. Uscinski (Ed.), *Conspiracy theories & the people who believe them* (pp. 245-256). Oxford University Press.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics and internal consistency of the main measures reported in the present study and their potential differences across the two waves of data collection

variable	First wave			Second wave			paired t-test		
	<i>M</i>	SD	α	<i>M</i>	SD	α	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
<i>Actors blamed for the war</i>									
Blaming Ukraine for war	4.82	3.48	–	5.92	3.12	–	12.47	< .001	.48
Blaming Russia for war	7.61	2.79	–	7.87	2.60	–	3.22	.001	.12
Blaming USA for war	5.45	3.66	–	6.27	3.14	–	10.01	< .001	.38
<i>Conspiracy beliefs</i>									
Pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs	2.54	1.09	.92	2.61	1.14	.93	3.17	.002	.12
Generic conspiracy beliefs	2.49	1.14	.93	2.54	1.18	.94	2.23	.026	.09
Anti-Western conspiracy	–	–	–	2.91	1.25	–	–	–	–
Anti-Russian conspiracy	–	–	–	2.86	0.98	–	–	–	–
<i>Symbolic threat variables</i>									
Symbolic threat: Western societies	2.78	1.30	–	2.79	1.34	–	0.313	.75	.01
Symbolic threat: European union	2.70	1.32	–	2.77	1.38	–	1.89	.06	.07
Symbolic threat: USA	3.05	1.41	–	3.02	1.46	–	0.883	.38	.03
Symbolic threat West composite	2.84	1.26	.94	2.86	1.32	.94	0.515	.61	.02
Symbolic threat: Russia	3.15	1.30	–	3.01	1.28	–	3.05	.002	.12

Note. The table shows descriptive statistics and internal consistency estimates (where available) for the main measures reported in the present study. The columns on the right show the potential statistical differences in those measures that were taken at both of the times of data collection analyzed via a paired *t*-test.

Table 2. The summary of hierarchical linear regression analyses showing the relationship between belief in pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories and symbolic threat from the West and Russia

Predictors (all are measured at T1)	Pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories T2		Symbolic threat from the West T2		Symbolic threat from Russia T2	
	β	95% CI	β	95% CI	β	95% CI
<i>Step 1</i>	<i>adj. R² = .755***</i>		<i>adj. R² = .705***</i>		<i>adj. R² = .372***</i>	
Age	.05*	.011, .088	.05*	.005, .086	-.03	-.090, .034
Gender	.02	-.021, .056	-.02	-.064, .017	-.01	-.073, .050
Education	-.05*	-.090, -.009	.01	-.029, .057	.00	-.064, .067
Subjective SES	.01	-.033, .046	-.01	-.050, .034	-.01	-.070, .057
Cognitive reflection	-.03	-.070, .011	.00	-.040, .045	.03	-.031, .098
Need for cognitive closure	-.01	-.051, .030	.01	-.033, .054	-.00	-.069, .063
Concern for war	-.02	-.073, .025	.00	-.048, .055	-.01	-.091, .066
Helplessness	-.04	-.088, .012	.03	-.027, .079	.08	-.004, .156
Political liberalism	.01	-.039, .050	-.08***	-.129, -.034	.01	-.059, .084
Preference for liberal gov.	-.06**	-.099, -.013	-.04	-.085, .006	.01	-.056, .082
Political cynicism	.10***	.054, .136	.06**	.017, .104	.02	-.051, .082
Right-wing authoritarianism	-.00	-.043, .038	.01	-.033, .052	.06	-.007, .123
Symbolic threat West	–	–	.56***	.496, .622	–	–
Symbolic threat Russia	–	–	–	–	.54***	.467, .606
pro-Kremlin conspiracy	.61***	.544, .670	–	–	–	–
<i>Step 2</i>	<i>$\Delta R^2 = .013***$</i>		<i>$\Delta R^2 = .028***$</i>		<i>$\Delta R^2 = .012***$</i>	
Symbolic threat West	.17***	.108, .226	–	–	-.10*	-.195, -.004
Symbolic threat Russia	-.08***	-.127, -.041	-.05*	-.097, -.006	–	–
pro-Kremlin conspiracy	–	–	.24***	.172, .306	-.06	-.158, .046
<i>Full model</i>	<i>adj. R² = .763***</i>		<i>adj. R² = .732***</i>		<i>adj. R² = .382***</i>	

Note. The table shows the results of final models of a series of hierarchical linear regressions predicting pro-Kremlin conspiracy beliefs and the sense of symbolic threat from the West and Russia at the second wave of the data collection while controlling for autoregressive effects of these variables at the first wave of the data collection. Standardized regression coefficients (β 's) and their 95% confidence intervals are presented for every predictor at the final step of the model. Also, the table shows the adjusted R^2 as well as change in R^2 for every step of the model. Significant predictors ($p < .05$) are presented in bold. Gender was coded as 1 = "men", 2 = "women". * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Table 3. The summary of hierarchical linear regression analyses showing the relationship between attribution of blame for the war in Ukraine, belief in pro-Kremlin conspiracy theories and symbolic threat from the West and Russia

Predictors (all are measured at T1)	Blaming Russia for the war in Ukraine T2		Blaming USA for the war in Ukraine T2		Blaming Ukraine for the war in Ukraine T2	
	β	95% CI	β	95% CI	β	95% CI
<i>Step 1</i>	<i>adj. R² = .489***</i>		<i>adj. R² = .656***</i>		<i>adj. R² = .576***</i>	
Blaming Russia T1	.47***	.404, .541	–	–	–	–
Blaming USA T1	–	–	.57***	.501, .639	–	–
Blaming Ukraine T1	–	–	–	–	.47***	.402, .536
<i>Step 2</i>	<i>$\Delta R^2 = .065***$</i>		<i>$\Delta R^2 = .036***$</i>		<i>$\Delta R^2 = .070***$</i>	
Symbolic threat West	-.15***	-.224, -.072	.10**	.030, .169	.15***	.080, .218
Symbolic threat Russia	.13***	.066, .184	-.06*	-.106, -.013	-.05	-.096, .005
pro-Kremlin conspiracy	-.15***	-.237, -.065	.20***	.125, .271	.25***	.171, .330
<i>Full model</i>	<i>adj. R² = .552***</i>		<i>adj. R² = .691***</i>		<i>adj. R² = .645***</i>	

Note. The table shows the results of final models of a series of hierarchical linear regressions predicting attribution of blame for the war in Ukraine to Russia, USA, and Ukraine at the second wave of the data collection while controlling for autoregressive effects of these variables at the first wave of the data collection. Standardized regression coefficients (β 's) and their 95% confidence intervals are presented for every predictor at the final step of the model. Also, the table shows the adjusted R^2 as well as change in R^2 for every step of the model. Significant predictors ($p < .05$) are presented in bold. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Table 4. Correlations of anti-West and anti-Russia conspiracy theory beliefs with the sense of symbolic threat from the West and Russia

	Correlation with the symbolic threat from the West (T2)	Correlation with the symbolic threat from Russia (T2)
<i>Anti-West conspiracy theories composite</i>	.73***	-.30***
Protests in the year 1989 that lead to the fall of the Communist regime were orchestrated and paid for by the western powers.	.60***	-.23***
EU and Brussels dictate to Slovakia what it has to do without Slovakia being able to influence it at all.	.70***	-.30***
<i>Anti-Russia conspiracy theories composite</i>	-.10**	.29***
During the invasion of Czechoslovakia by the armies of Warsaw pact in august 1968, many more people died than what was reported by the official sources but this was covered up by the communist regime.	-.06	.18***
Russian secret agents operate in Slovakia with the long-term goal to systematically exterminate pro-West politicians.	-.11**	.30***

Note. The table shows correlations between the sense of symbolic threat from the West and Russia and the two items of anti-West and two anti-Russia conspiracy theories (composites reflect averaged ratings for the two items). * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Table 5. Moderation analysis predicting beliefs in anti-West and anti-Russian conspiracy theories by symbolic threat from the West and Russia

	<i>Anti-West conspiracy belief (T2)</i>		<i>Anti-Russian conspiracy belief (T2)</i>	
	<i>estimate (SE)</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>estimate (SE)</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>Predictors (model 1)</i>				
Symbolic threat West (T2)	0.674 (0.025)	< .001	-0.086 (0.028)	.002
Analytic thinking (T1)	-0.027 (0.020)	.176	-0.056 (0.022)	.012
Interaction	0.042 (0.015)	.005	-0.013 (0.017)	.456
<i>Simple slope analysis</i>				
Low analytic thinking	0.605 (0.037)	< .001	-0.066 (0.042)	.115
Average analytic thinking	0.674 (0.025)	< .001	-0.086 (0.028)	.002
High analytic thinking	0.743 (0.033)	< .001	-0.107 (0.037)	.004
<i>Predictors (model 2)</i>				
Symbolic threat Russia (T2)	-0.281 (0.035)	< .001	0.222 (0.028)	< .001
Analytic thinking (T1)	-0.125 (0.027)	< .001	-0.048 (0.022)	.025
Interaction	-0.039 (0.020)	.053	0.002 (0.016)	.917
<i>Simple slope analysis</i>				
Low analytic thinking	-0.216 (0.049)	< .001	0.219 (0.039)	< .001
Average analytic thinking	-0.281 (0.035)	< .001	0.222 (0.028)	< .001
High analytic thinking	-0.346 (0.049)	< .001	0.225 (0.039)	< .001

Note. The table shows results of four moderation analyses predicting belief in anti-West and anti-Russian conspiracy theories with symbolic threat from the West or Russia as predictors and analytic thinking (cognitive reflection) as a moderator. For all moderations, the table also shows the results of a simple slope analysis summarizing the effect of symbolic threat on conspiracy theory belief at three levels of analytic thinking (average, and one standard deviation below/above average).